

You Don't Have to Live Next to Me: Towards Demobilizing Individualistic Bias in Computational Approaches to Urban Segregation

Anastassia Vybornova*^{1,2} and Trivik Verma³

¹Copenhagen Center for Social Data Science (SODAS), University of Copenhagen

²NETworks, Data, and Society (NERDS), IT University of Copenhagen

³Bristol Digital Futures Institute and the School for Policy Studies, University of Bristol

GISRUK 2025

Summary

Segregation, conceptualized as the spatial expression of social inequalities, is a common phenomenon across different urban contexts. The increasing popularity of Big Data and computational models has inspired many computational studies on urban segregation. However, these studies are often epistemologically interdependent with prevalent economic theories, which have a hyperfocus on individual responsibility while neglecting systemic processes. We outline how individualistic bias impacts (de)segregation policies, and how disregarding data ethics leads to further marginalization of disadvantaged groups. Our essay suggests revisiting our computational processes to demobilize individualistic bias, fostering instead a collective, conscious, and systemic approach toward inequalities.

KEYWORDS: urban segregation, spatial inequalities, individualistic bias, Big Data, racial capitalism

1 Mathematics in the Ghetto

In this essay, we offer a critical analysis of computational approaches to urban segregation. We argue that many of these approaches run the risk of overfocusing on the individual while neglecting systemic processes. We trace how this mental model, commonly known as individualistic bias, enters computational approaches to segregation through their epistemological interdependence with prevalent economic theories, thereby hindering contributions to systemic change. Understanding segregation as the *spatial manifestation of social inequalities* (Blokland, 2008), we argue that a longer-term ambition to mitigate these inequalities needs to operate on systemic rather than individual level; and we highlight the pitfalls of computational models that tend to do the opposite. At the example of recent (de)segregation policies across several European countries, we illustrate

*anvy@itu.dk

how the increasing popularity of Big Data gives way to a data-driven essentialism, thereby further exacerbating pre-existing inequalities.

We then outline how individualistic bias extends beyond computational modeling and permeates public discourse, policy-making, and education – spheres in which we relate to each other as humans in public space. We further argue that these issues are exacerbated by recent developments in artificial intelligence and the datafication of governance. In the digital age, doing Mathematics in the Ghetto without ever having experienced the Ghetto has become very easy. Our hope is to instead shift attention of our models towards explicitly exposing and encoding systemic drivers of segregation, persuading us to critically engage with the sociopolitical and real-world implications of abstract modeling processes, and reflecting on our own positionality. With an appeal to our fellow computational scientists, our vision is that this commentary will foster a conscious, community-oriented focus on reducing systemic urban inequalities.

2 Inequality reduction as a moral dilemma

There is a deeper implication to centering inequalities – both in our learning about urban segregation, and in our ambitions to contribute to social change more broadly speaking. By today, the call to *reduce inequalities* has become largely commonplace (UN, 2024). All too often, however, there is a mismatch of underlying philosophical positions between what is being laid out as the future vision – namely, eradicating all inequalities – and what is being proposed as pathway there – namely, individualistic meritocracy. This is the predicament of the Engineering-Economy Complex¹ (EEC). In plain terms, many people who declare to be working towards inequality reduction do not, themselves, believe that all inequalities can, nor should, be eradicated (Simon, 2016). While the latter is an arguable philosophical position, trouble ensues when such position is being kept implicit, effectively constraining the solution space, while getting obscured in the discursive framing of the ultimate goal.

3 Causes and consequences of urban spatial inequalities

To better understand the epistemological underpinning of computational segregation models, we review the prevalent streams of research on segregation causes. Most research focuses on socioeconomic differences (Park, 1925; Logan, 1978), residential preferences (Thernstrom, Stephan and Thernstrom, Abigail, 1997), discriminatory stances (Massey and Lundy, 2001), housing search practices, or a combination thereof (Krysan and Crowder, 2017). We then show that most of these approaches scrutinize *individual* agency to explain why segregation arises and persists. This logical arrow of causal reasoning is in line with an understanding of segregation as emergent (macro-level) property of a complex system of (micro-level) individual agents (Schelling, 1978; Wiley, 1988; Stadtfeld, 2018). Most computational approaches to segregation operate with this conceptualization (from micro to macro). This lens, while relevant, does not paint the full picture, since the arrow

¹The “Engineering-Economy Complex”, in short EEC, is a term under which we cluster all work that operates in the solution space of engineering, with epistemological underpinnings from economic theory; many data-driven or computational approaches fall under this category.

of causality goes both ways: the macro-level pre-determines the solution space in which individuals on the micro-level can operate.

How consequences of segregation are conceptualized has a far-reaching epistemological impact for any study of segregation. In particular, segregation is often framed as an isolated and individualized problem of the poor, thus rendering larger structures of oppression invisible. We deem it necessary to go beyond acknowledging the suffering of the disadvantaged and explicitly acknowledge the agency and accountability of those who *benefit* from the dominant systems of oppression – including ourselves. In our review of consequences of segregation, we therefore ask: *cui bono?*, and sketch the positive outcomes of segregation for advantaged communities, such as socioeconomic benefits driving racial capitalism (Lipman, 2018; Lipsitz, 2011), gate-keeping in education and personal networks (Tilly, 2009; Otero et al., 2022; Jæger, 2022), and spatially unequal distribution of health risks (Tehrani et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2020). Lastly, we argue that segregation also has a moral function: when we are not being directly confronted with the concentration of disadvantage, it is easier for us to accept (or outwardly ignore) that this disadvantage exists, and that we are benefitting from it (Kelly, 2004; Mijs and Usmani, 2024).

4 Computational approaches to urban segregation and their policy impacts

The strategic collection and use of Big Data in support of political projects such as nation-building is by no means a new phenomenon (Anderson, 1983). However, in the last few years we have witnessed an unparalleled increase in public interest in artificial intelligence, with spillovers to a wide range of knowledge domains, including urban planning and policy-making. Together with the increased availability of large-scale data sets, and the progressively lowered bar of how much privacy-intruding collection of personal data we are willing to accept (Thompson and Warzel, 2019), this helps explain that *data-driven* approaches are becoming more and more popular for policy-making (Kandt and Batty, 2021). We argue that the discursive hype around artificial intelligence and Big Data substantially impacts, and potentially misleads, computational approaches to urban segregation through a phenomenon which we call ‘New Essentialism’. We then showcase how New Essentialism affects different computational approaches to urban segregation, namely spatial segregation indices (Spierenburg et al., 2023), agent-based modeling (Liebe et al., 2023), and machine learning and forecasting endeavours (Lum and Isaac, 2016; Georgati, 2023). Finally, we illustrate the pitfalls of individualistic bias and New Essentialism for policy-making through several contemporary examples such as the ‘Ghetto laws’ in Denmark (Risager, 2023) and the ‘Act on Extraordinary Measures for Urban Problems’ in the Netherlands (Uitermark et al., 2017).

5 You Don’t Have to Live Next to Me

In conclusion, we identify the spatial manifestation of social inequalities in contemporary cities as intrinsically entangled with, and constrained by, capitalist relations. Further, we argue that under these given constraints, individual agency, choice or preference with relation to place is not a helpful category for analysis of existing spatial inequalities. Instead, we suggest that computational approaches to urban segregation should seek to alleviate inequalities independently of place. Con-

sidering social inequalities to be an issue of distribution rather than representation (Sarbo, 2022), the issue that we propose to tackle is not how to prevent marginalized groups from living together (Shelby, 2014), but rather how to counteract the conditions that produce marginalized groups, independently of where they live. *You don't have to live next to me*, Nina Simone sings in 'Mississippi Goddamn', and continues by demanding: *Just give me my equality*.

6 Acknowledgements

For helpful comments and engaged discussions, our sincere gratefulness goes to Anne de Koeijer, Carolina Niewöhner, Björn Karlsson, Rainer Hegselmann, Gerwin van Schie, Martin Fleischmann, Gülşah Akçakır, Chanuwas Aswamenakul, and Dave Feldman.

7 Author biographies

Anastassia Vybornova is a postdoctoral researcher in Urban Data Science at the Copenhagen Center for Social Data Science (SODAS) at the University of Copenhagen and at the NETwoRks, Data, and Society (NERDS) research group at the IT University of Copenhagen. She has a background in Technical Physics and Environmental Science. Her current work focuses on sustainable mobility and the spatiality of social networks.

Trivik Verma is an Associate Professor at the Bristol Digital Futures Institute and the School for Policy Studies, University of Bristol. His research focusses on cities, inequalities, and justice. He studies various challenges of urbanisation such as segregation, inequities in access and wellbeing, transport and energy poverty, and climate-related vulnerabilities.

References

- Anderson, B. (1983). *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. Verso.
- Blokland, T. (2008). From the outside Looking in: A “European” Perspective on the *Ghetto*. *City & Community*, 7(4), 372–377, https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6040.2008.00271_5.x http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1111/j.1540-6040.2008.00271_5.x.
- Georgati, M. (2023). *Disaggregation of population estimates at high spatial resolution with machine learning*. PhD thesis, Aalborg Universitet. Publisher: Aalborg Universitetsforlag.
- Jæger, M. M. (2022). Cultural capital and educational inequality: an assessment of the state of the art. In K. Gërkhani, N. De Graaf, & W. Raub (Eds.), *Handbook of Sociological Science* (pp. 121–134). Edward Elgar Publishing <https://www.elgaronline.com/view/book/9781789909432/book-part-9781789909432-15.xml>.
- Kandt, J. & Batty, M. (2021). Smart cities, big data and urban policy: Towards urban analytics for the long run. *Cities*, 109, 102992, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102992> <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264275120313408>.

- Kelly, T. (2004). Practical Rationality in Social Scientific Explanation: The Case of Residential Segregation. *Philosophy of the Social Sciences*, 34(1), 3–19, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0048393103260773> <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0048393103260773>.
- Krysan, M. & Crowder, K. (2017). *Cycle of Segregation: Social Processes and Residential Stratification*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Liebe, U., van Cranenburgh, S., & Chorus, C. (2023). Maximizing Utility or Avoiding Losses? Uncovering Decision Rule-Heterogeneity in Sociological Research with an Application to Neighbourhood Choice. *Sociological Methods & Research*, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00491241231186657>.
- Lipman, P. (2018). Segregation, the “Black Spatial Imagination,” and Radical Social Transformation. *Democracy and Education*, 26(2) <https://democracyeducationjournal.org/home/vol26/iss2/9/>.
- Lipsitz, G. (2011). *How Racism Takes Place*. Temple University Press.
- Logan, J. R. (1978). Growth, Politics, and the Stratification of Places. *American Journal of Sociology*, 84(2), 404–416, <https://doi.org/10.1086/226790>. Publisher: The University of Chicago Press <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/226790>.
- Lum, K. & Isaac, W. (2016). To Predict and Serve? *Significance*, 13(5), 14–19, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1740-9713.2016.00960.x> <https://academic.oup.com/jrssi/article/13/5/14/7029190>.
- Massey, D. S. & Lundy, G. (2001). Use of Black English and Racial Discrimination in Urban Housing Markets: New Methods and Findings. *Urban Affairs Review*, 36(4), 452–469, <https://doi.org/10.1177/10780870122184957>. Publisher: SAGE Publications Inc <https://doi.org/10.1177/10780870122184957>.
- Mijs, J. J. B. & Usmani, A. (2024). How Segregation Ruins Inference: A Sociological Simulation of the Inequality Equilibrium. *Social Forces*, 103(1), 45–65, <https://doi.org/10.1093/sf/soae033> <https://doi.org/10.1093/sf/soae033>.
- Otero, G., Volker, B., & Rozer, J. (2022). Space and social capital: social contacts in a segregated city. *Urban Geography*, 43(10), 1638–1661, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2021.1950982> <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02723638.2021.1950982>.
- Park, R. E. (1925). The Urban Community as a Spatial Pattern and a Moral Order. In *The Urban Community. Selected Papers from the Proceedings of the American Sociological Society*. Chicago: The Chicago University Press.
- Risager, B. S. (2023). Territorial stigmatization and housing commodification under racial neoliberalism: The case of Denmark’s ‘ghettos’. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 55(4), 850–870, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X221141427> <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0308518X221141427>.

- Sarbo, B. (2022). Rassismus und gesellschaftliche Produktionsverhältnisse. Ein materialistischer Rassismusbegriff. In *Die Diversität der Ausbeutung. Zur Kritik des herrschenden Antirassismus* (pp. 37–63).
- Schelling, T. C. (1978). *Micromotives and macrobehavior*. Fels lectures on public policy analysis. New York: Norton, [new ed.] with a new preface and the nobel lecture. edition.
- Shelby, T. (2014). Integration, Inequality, and Imperatives of Justice: A Review Essay. *Philosophy & Public Affairs*, 42(3), 253–285, <https://doi.org/10.1111/papa.12034> <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/papa.12034>.
- Simon, R. (2016). The Conflict Paradigm in Sociology and the Study of Social Inequality: Paradox and Possibility. *Theory in Action*, 9(1), 1–31, <https://doi.org/10.3798/tia.1937-0237.16001> <http://transformativestudies.org/wp-content/uploads/10.3798tia.1937-0237.16001.pdf>.
- Spierenburg, L., van Cranenburgh, S., & Cats, O. (2023). Characterizing residential segregation in cities using intensity, separation, and scale indicators. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 103, 101990, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2023.101990> <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0198971523000534>.
- Stadtfeld, C. (2018). The Micro-Macro Link in Social Networks <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3211795>.
- Tehrani, S. O., Wu, S. J., & Roberts, J. D. (2019). The Color of Health: Residential Segregation, Light Rail Transit Developments, and Gentrification in the United States. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(19), 3683, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16193683>. Number: 19 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/16/19/3683>.
- Thernstrom, Stephan & Thernstrom, Abigail (1997). *America in black and white: one nation, indivisible*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Thompson, S. A. & Warzel, C. (2019). Smartphones Are Spies. Here's Whom They Report To. *The New York Times* <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2019/12/20/opinion/location-tracking-smartphone-marketing.html>.
- Tilly, C. (2009). *Durable inequality*. Univ. of California Press.
- Uitermark, J., Hochstenbach, C., & Van Gent, W. (2017). The statistical politics of exceptional territories. *Political Geography*, 57, 60–70, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polgeo.2016.11.011> <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S096262981630258X>.
- UN (2024). Sustainable development goals: Goal 10 https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal10#progress_and_info.
- Wiley, N. (1988). The Micro-Macro Problem in Social Theory. *Sociological Theory*, 6(2), 254, <https://doi.org/10.2307/202119> <https://www.jstor.org/stable/202119?origin=crossref>.

Yang, T.-C., Park, K., & Matthews, S. A. (2020). Racial/ethnic segregation and health disparities: Future directions and opportunities. *Sociology Compass*, *14*(6), e12794, <https://doi.org/10.1111/soc4.12794> <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/soc4.12794>.